
Innovative Management of Functional Adult Continuing Education for Leadership and Sustainable National Development in Cross River State

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Abstract

This study sets out to examine the role of well managed adult continuing education, innovation and re-orientation of leadership value for sustainable national development. It adopts the survey technique since it involves a group of people by analyzing collected data from few members considered to be representative fraction of the entire population. A total of one hundred and ten (110) respondents who were randomly selected participated in the study. Three research questions and three hypotheses were accordingly investigated, to show the relevance of management of adult continuing education efficiently and its implications to nation sustainable development. The (X^2) values of the variables were 4.02 and 43.6 respectively; compared to the critical value of 7.62. The hypotheses which stated that the level of adult continuing education efficiently managed will not have influence on the role play in adult continuing education and sustainable development by reducing poverty was upheld or rejected.

Introduction

In every organisation, it is very necessary for new phase of things, innovation as the process of introducing or developing a new idea, practice or product which, if successful, results in the capability of doing something that could not be done or at least not so well or so economically. Nelson in Nduanya (n.d) the word of Carless (2013) opines that innovation is an attempt to bring

about educational improvement by doing something which is perceived to be different or new. The main rationale for change is indicative of the ubiquity of innovations. It may help schools to keep up-to-date with the latest development or research findings and can also be force to encourage educational quality and fairer opportunity for diverse section of society. Educational change may also contribute to the development of economic competitiveness.

The effectiveness of any organisation depends greatly on innovative management for its functioning hence management of an organisation involves the process of organising and controlling. Management is defined as the systematic organisation of economic resources and its task makes these resources productive, Drucker in Akpan (2011). Accordingly UNESCO (1979) defines management as a social process which is designed to ensure the cooperation, participation and involvement of others in the effective achievement of a given or predetermined objective. Ogumu (2000) reviewed management as the effective organisational and utilisation of human and material resources in particular system for the achievement of identified objective. In the world of Macfarland (1979) management as the process by which managers create, direct, maintain and operate purposive organisations through coordinated, cooperative human effort.

Therefore, towards goal can be described as the process of coordinating and integrating both human and material resources of an organisation towards goal attainment. In other words, it emphasizes systematic organisation of resources for carrying out of institutional processes and the execution of work. Hence, innovative management of functional adult continuing education can contribute positively to sustainable national development.

Adult education means all kinds of learning undertaken by everyone who is an adult. Any man or woman who is learning anything new for acquiring information and understanding or learning how to appreciate or appreciating things or liking or disliking things new or having a new feeling about anything, or learning a skill how to manipulate anything with integration of the body is engaged in adult education (Ani, 2010). Nzeneri (1999) viewed adult education as any type of education programme undertaken by matured man, woman and youth outside the formal schooling system to acquire functional skills. The notion of adult education is often used interchangeably with other notions such as adult literacy, adult basic education, lifelong learning and continuing education. Adult education in its ramifications accommodates all forms of education: formal, non-formal and informal. It is for self and national development, for cultural awareness and integration for conscientisation and group dynamism. The National Policy on Education (2004) states that mass literacy, adult and non-formal education encompass all forms of functional education given to youth and adults outside the formal school system such as functional literacy and vocational education. Adult education does not only equip an individual to earn a living but also help him to enjoy life so that the individual can make apposite and worthwhile contribution to the community in which he lives. Literacy is both a process of skills acquisition for productive and purposeful life in the society and a product of organised intellectual schemes and effort it is therefore a tool for man's total empowerment. Consequently, literacy is sine-qua-non for transforming Nigeria.

The ability to read and write constitute the right to basic education, defined as literacy, which allows all adults to engage actively in and to transform the nation Nigeria and indeed the world. Literacy that makes one engage actively in national transformation is functional literacy, Functional literacy is the magic wand for the building of a total man and for every form of development, Grey in (Cook, 1999) viewed functional literacy as skill used by those engaging effectively in all the activities in which literacy produces desired goals. Functional literacy is achievement and occupational-oriented, according to Edukugho (2008). A former Minister of

State disclosed that 56 percent of Nigeria's population of over 140 million people had attained literacy level while only 44 percent are still illiterate. This is cheering news considering the collective commitments adopted by the world Education Forum, Dakar, Senegal, which took place in 2000 to the attainment of Education For All (EFA) goal and targets for every citizen and for every society.

According to the Dakar framework for action, there should be achievement of 50 percent improvement in levels of literacy by 2015 especially for women and equitable access to basic and continuing education for all adults. The effect of the read campaign which was introduced in May, 2008 has manifested. The read campaign was mounted in a bid to restore the culture of reading and writing among the people. The success of adult literacy efforts will lead to lifelong learning, sustainable livelihood, and good wealth, active and productive citizenry and improved quality of life for individuals, communities and the entire Nigeria society. Literacy and continuing education are vital for eradication of poverty and the empowerment of women and gender balance.

Onyishi in Chukwuma Obire and Ejiugwu (2012) defined adult and non-formal education as efforts at improving the provision and implantation of development programmes which have basic education or training component. Such programmes provision usually take place outside formal education system whose process is without the rigid forms of traditional schooling such as regimented curricula, classroom arrangements and set syllabus strictly maintained. It is a process which aims at empowering poor people - both the advantaged group and those who had been kept out of decision-making structures in the society. In the words of Hassan (2009), it is any organised, systematic education activities outside the framework of formal school system designed to provide selective type of learning to particular sub-groups in the population, adults as well as children. It includes lifelong learning which is learning activity undertaken throughout life with the aim of improving knowledge, skills and competence within a personal, civic, and social and/or employment related perspective. Adult education is continuing education and training that deals exclusively with efficiency and employability, adding both subjective and objective educational concerns. Egbezor and Okanezi (2008) identified ANFE programmes as functional literacy education and life skill training. These programmes are designed to empower and impart ability to function in daily life, society and in the environment (community) in which people find themselves. They are given alongside with literacy and numeracy, social awareness and functionality components.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to find out the challenges of innovative management of functional continuing education for leadership and sustainable national development.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What will enhance the status of adult continuing education facilities for quality training of leadership and sustainable development?
2. What challenges do adults continuing education managers have in their effort to provide quality leadership and sustainable development adult continuing education

3. Will the level management bring about sustainable development?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- a. The enhanced status of education facilities for quality training of leadership will bring about adult education and sustainable development.
- b. The challenges of adult continuing education will not bring about sustainable development.
- c. The level of adult continuing education will not have significant influence on sustainable development.

Method

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Descriptive survey design enables a researcher to report “conditions or relationships that exist; practices that prevail; beliefs, points of views, or attitudes that are held; processes that are going on; effects that are being felt; or trends that are developing” (Cohen, Manion and Morrison in Obi 2012). The design is suitable for this study because it provides appropriate methodology for opinion.

Area of the Study

This study was carried out in the three education zones of Cross River State of Nigeria. The zones used for the study are Calabar, Ikom and Ogoja zones.

Population

The population comprised of all adult in three education zones for the study.

Sampling and Technique

The sample for this study is a random of $\frac{1}{3}$ sample by replacement drawn from the total population of 330 which yielded one hundred and ten (110) respondents that were used for the research.

Instruments for Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire which consists of twelve items type; titled management and innovation for adult continuing education for leadership value (MIACELV) was used to measure management of adult continuing education and sustainable development. A4-point likert scale was used to measure responses to the questionnaire. The weighting of the responses were;

- | | | |
|----------------|---|--------------|
| Strongly agree | - | 4 points |
| Agree | - | 3 points |
| Disagree | - | 2 points and |

Strongly disagree - 1 point

Validation of the Instrument

The instrument was face validated by lecturers; one each from department of adult continuing education, measurement and evaluation from University of Calabar. The experts recommendations were effected before the final copy of the instrument was prepared.

Method of Data Collection

The researchers were helped by three research assistants from each zone to distribute copies of questionnaire to adults. In each of the zones, the respondents were allowed same time to fill the questionnaire and were later retrieved for statistical analysis.

Method of Data Analysis

Analyzing the data collected, chi-square (X^2) was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 significant level.

Result

Table1: Showing enhanced status of adult continuing facilities for quality training leadership and sustainable development.

Variables	N	X	SD	Cal- x^2	Tabs	Percent
Quality leadership and sustainable development	108	3.6	1.1	44.5	7.62	Significant
Management of adult Continuing Education Facilities	108	4.1	1.0			

Significant: Df = 3; $p < 0.05$

The data in table 1 shows that x^2 of 44.5 was greater than the critical value of 7.62, hence, the hypothesis that enhanced status of adult continuing education facilities for quality training leadership will not bring about sustainable development was not accepted.

Table 2 is showing challenges of adult continuing education manager in their effort to provide quality leadership and sustainable development.

Variables	N	X	SD	Cal- x^2	Tabs	Percent
Quality leadership and sustainable development	108	3.6	1.2	44.5	7.62	Significant
Management of adult	108	4.1	1.0			

Continuing Education Facilities						
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Significant: Df = 3; p<0.05

The calculated χ^2 value of 44.5 is less than 7.62 at 0.05 significance with 3 as the degree of freedom. The null hypothesis which states that the challenges of adult continuing education managers have in their effort to provide quality leadership and sustainable development was upheld or rejected.

It was also evident from the result that adult continuing education has a quite number of challenges facing its effective implementation. These challenges affect effective implementation of adult continuing programmes at the formal higher institutional and non-formal education centres where teaching-learning takes place. One of the major challenges inhibiting the development of education and its other sub-sectors in Nigeria is inadequate funding. According to Igbuzor (2006), there are a lot of challenges facing Nigeria and making it difficult for good quality education that is empowering and capable of bringing about sustainable development to be provided.

Table 3 shows the level of adult continuing education that bring about sustainable development.

Variables	N	X	SD	Cal- χ^2	Tabs	Percent
Quality leadership and sustainable development	108	3.1	1.1	40.2	7.62	Significant
Management of adult	108	4.6	1.0			
Continuing Education Facilities						

Significant: Df = 3; p<0.05

In table 3, the level of adult continuing education brings about sustainable development. The Mean (x) – value of 40.2 was found to be significant statistically as it is the table value of 7.62 at 0.05 significant level with 3 as the degree of freedom.

Discussion of Findings

Findings of the study revealed that the hypothesis relating to enhanced status of education facilities for quality training of leaders was statistically significant. The result of which confirms the assertion of these adult education experts (Hassan, 2009, Obanya, 2010, Onyiah, 2004) who argued that innovative management of functional adult continuing education programme will entrench empowerment leader for sustainable national development. Furthermore, Igbuzor (2006) said that importance of education to human cannot be overemphasized because its importance and linkages to the development of any society is well known.

It was also revealed in the study result that the challenges of Adult Continuing Education and sustainable development was statistically significant. If it is properly addressed, adult education can contribute to human development in areas of poverty reduction (Harbans, 2004).

Finally, the result of the study revealed that the hypothesis relating to the level of adult continuing education and sustainable development was statistically significant.

Conclusion

It was concluded from the study that lack of enhanced status of educational facilities for quality training in adult education, hampers the realization of adult learners and sustainable development. Adult continuing education should be given its right place in the society to boost and promote adult empowerment for leadership and sustainable development.

Recommendations.

It is recommended that:

1. An inventory for all the existing adult continuing education should be carried out for effective planning
2. Networking by all stakeholders should be encourage
3. Working conditions of adult instructors should be improved.

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